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Synthesis of 2-(2-Acetamidophenoxy)-4-anilino-6-phenylureas-S-triazine and Study of Their Antibacterial Activity

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UREA derivatives possess wide therapeutic activities, such as antibacterial¹, antithyroid, hypnotic and anesthetic, hypoglycemic², anthelmintic, diuretic³ and biocidal activity. Phenylacetamidourea derivatives are active anticonvulsants.

2-Acidamido group increases antipyretic activity^{4,5}. Moreover, salicylamide is more soluble than salicylic acid and has a more marked analgesic property. Salicylamide has a marked anthelmintic, antispasmodic, antipyretic and sedative action^{6,7}. Phenoxyethers of S-triazine are well-known fungicides⁸.

To study the antibacterial activity of compounds of the type 1 were synthesised by the condensation of cyanuric chloride (0.1 M) and aniline (0.1 M). The resulted product was afforded to react with salicylamide in equimolecular proportion. The compound obtained was made to condense with

various phenylureas to get the compounds of the type 1.

Experimental

Infrared spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Beckman IR-5 spectrometer equipped with NaCl prism.

4-Anilino-2,6-dichloro-S-triazine: Cyanuric chloride (0.1 mol) and aniline (0.1 mol) in dioxane or acetone were refluxed for 3 h on water-bath at pH 9.2 by adding aqueous NaOH (2%). The clear solution thus obtained was added in crushed ice and then filtered, washed with dil. HCl and crystallised from ethanol (80%), m.p. 163°.

2-(2-Acetamidophenoxy)-4-anilino-6-chloro-S-triazine⁹: Salicylamide (0.01 mol) was dissolved in acetone and NaOH solution (5%) was added dropwise until the solution appeared clear. It was added dropwise during 1.5 h to a mechanically stirred solution of 4-anilino-2,6-dichloro-S-triazine (0.01 mol) in dioxane at 35°. The temperature was gradually increased at 45° during 2 h. The pH was maintained 9.2 by the addition of aqueous NaOH. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature. It was added in crushed ice and HCl solution (2%). The compound obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallised from benzene, m.p. 241-42°.

General method for preparation of 2-(2-acetamidophenoxy)-4-anilino-6-phenylurea-S-triazine: 2-(2-Acetamidophenoxy)-4-anilino-6-chloro-S-triazine (0.01 mol) and various phenylureas (0.015 mol) in acetone or dioxane were refluxed for-3 h on water-bath keeping pH of the solution at 9.2 by adding aqueous NaOH (2%). Clear solution was added in crushed ice, filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. The yield of the compounds varied from 69 to 82%; m.p. R₁ = phenyl, 165°; o-tolyl, 185°; m-tolyl, 157°; p-tolyl, 145°; m-nitrophenyl, 114°; p-nitrophenyl, 120°; o-chlorophenyl, 160°; m-chlorophenyl, 130°; p-chlorophenyl, 192°.

Antibacterial activity: The purified product was screened for antibacterial activity by cup-plate method using a species of gram-positive bacteria, i.e. *S. aureus*, and a species of gram-negative bacteria, i.e. *E. coli*. Testing was carried out in ethanol solution at the concentration of 10 mg ml⁻¹. The zone of inhibition of the test solutions were recorded.

The zone of inhibition was found considerable for the species, *i.e.* *S. aureus* in the case of 2-(2-acetamidophenoxy)-4-anilino-6-phenylurea-*S*-triazine and 2-(2-acetamidophenoxy)-4-anilino-6-*o*-tolylurea-*S*-triazine (2.5 and 2.0 m.m., respectively). While the marked zone of inhibition was obtained for *E. coli* against 2-(2-acetamidophenoxy)-4-anilino-6-*m*-tolylurea-*S*-triazine and 2-(2-acetamidophenoxy)-4-anilino-6-*p*-nitrophenylurea-*S*-triazine (3 and 2 m.m., respectively.)

Infrared spectra : All the compounds in general recorded the following bands, N-H bending, 1540-1510 ; C-O stretching 1660-1600 ; C-O-C stretching 1240-1200 ; and C₈N₈ stretching 850-780 cm⁻¹.

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A Flavone Glycoside from Seeds of *Cassia spectabilis* DC

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IN an earlier communication¹ isolation of two anthraquinones and a flavone glycoside from the seeds of *Cassia spectabilis* DC along with the structural studies of the two anthraquinone derivatives had been reported. The present communication deals with the structural studies of the flavone glycoside.

The brown coloured flavone glycoside, C₂₈H₂₄O₁₁ when hydrolysed with ethanolic hydrochloric acid, gave glucose (PC, osazone) and an aglycone, C₁₇H₁₄O₆. On the basis of standard colour reactions², spectral data^{3,4} and chemical degradation studies, the aglycone has been identified as 5,4'-dihydroxy-7,3'-dimethoxyflavone (velutin).

The aglycone showed bathochromic shift with aluminium chloride but the glycoside did not, indicating thereby that the glucose molecule is attached to the hydroxyl group at position 5. On periodate oxidation two moles of periodate per mole of the glycoside were consumed producing one mole of formic acid which showed that the sugar glucose is in the pyranose form. The hydrolysability of the glycoside by emulsin showed the presence of β-linkage.

The aglycone, velutin had been reported earlier from plant sources⁵ and it had been also synthesised⁶. Recently, a glycoside of velutin⁷, 4'-hydroxy-7,3'-dimethoxyflavone-5-*O*-α-L(-) rhamnopyranoside has been reported from the seeds of *Cassia nodose*. But the glycoside in the present communication, 4'-hydroxy-7,3'-dimethoxyflavone-5-*O*-β-D(+)-glucopyranoside, isolated from the seeds of *Cassia spectabilis* is reported for the first time.

Experimental

Isolation and purification of the glycoside has been described in an earlier communication¹.

Hydrolysis : The glycoside (200 mg) was hydrolysed using 7% ethanolic hydrochloric acid (25 ml) under reflux for 6 h, ethanol distilled off and the aglycone crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 225° (Found : C, 64.70 ; H, 4.70. C₁₇H₁₄O₆ calcd. C, 65.00 ; H, 4.50%) ; acetate (Ac₂O/Py), m.p. 207° (Found : acetyl 20. C₁₇H₁₂O₆(COCH₃)₂ calcd. 21.60%) ; methyl ether (Me₂SO₄/K₂CO₃), m.p. 192° (Found : methoxy 32.92. C₁₅H₈O₂(OCH₃)₄ calcd. 36.26%) ; λ_{max} (EtOH) 268, 348 ; +AlCl₃ 268, 383 ; +NaOEt 293, 398 nm ; ν_{max} (KBr) 3440, 2950, 2850, 1180, 1660, 1605 and 845 cm⁻¹ ; δ (DMSO) 3.85 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.92 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.35 (1H, d, *J* 2.5, C-6), 6.75 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, C-8), 6.90 (1H, s, C-3), 7.01 (1H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, C-5), 7.60 (dd, *J* 2.5 Hz and 8.5 Hz, C-2', C-6').

Periodate oxidation : The glycoside (20 mg) was dissolved in ethanol (25 ml) and distilled water (25 ml), treated with 0.1 *M* sodium metaperiodate (25 ml) and the reaction mixture allowed to stand for 48 h. The amount of periodate consumed and formic acid liberated were estimated by titrimetric method of Hirst and Jones⁸. For each mole of the glycoside, 1.8 mole of periodate was consumed and 1.2 mole of formic acid liberated.

Enzymic hydrolysis : The glycoside (20 mg) was hydrolysed using emulsin prepared from almond⁹ at 40 to 50° for 12 h when D(+)-glucose was found in the hydrolysate(PC).

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